

77%), m.p. 205° (Found: C, 61.39; H, 3.90; N, 8.82. $C_{16}H_{13}N_2O_3S$ requires: C, 61.54; H, 3.85; N, 8.97%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 662, 1 535, 1 447, 1 375, 1 300, 1 272, 1 235, 1 168, 1 028, 920, 865, 755 and 628 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.76–7.33 (6H, m, N–C₆H₅ + C₉–H), 7.10 (1H, s, C₄–H), 6.16 (2H, s, OCH₂O) and 2.53 (3H, s, SCH₃).

6-Ethylthio-7-phenyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-8(7H)-one (2e): It was prepared by the above procedure by using ethyl bromide instead of methyl iodide. The product was crystallised from ethanol, yield (67%), m.p. 223° (Found: N, 8.48. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_3S$ requires: N, 8.59%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.67–7.26 (6H, m, N–C₆H₅ + C₉–H), 7.00 (1H, s, C₄–H), 6.10 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 3.13 (2H, q, SCH₂CH₃) and 1.33 (3H, t, SCH₂CH₃).

1,3-Dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-6,8(5H,7H)-dione (5): A mixture of **1** (1.95 g, 0.01 mol) and urea (3.0 g, 0.05 mol) was heated in an oil-bath at 110–15° for 30 min. The temperature was then raised to 150–60°. There was evolution of ammonia which ceased after 7–8 h. It was then cooled and the product crystallised from ethanol, (1.69 g, 82%), m.p. >300° (Found: C, 52.62; H, 2.99; N, 13.45. $C_9H_6N_2O_4$ requires: C, 52.42; H, 2.91; N, 13.59%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 350, 3 190 (N–H's), 1 670 (CO–N) and 1 642 (N–CO–N) cm^{-1} .

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. V. Kessar, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh, for facilities. One of the authors (S.B.G.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. S. S. BEDI and K. S. NARANG, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 253.
2. F. DALLACKER, *Monatsh Chem.*, 1959, 90, 846
3. E. OERTLY and A. PICTET, *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges.*, 1910, 43, 1336.
4. H. J. HESS, T. H. CRONIN and A. SCRIBANINE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 130.

Ursolic Acid from *Nepeta leucophylla* Benth.

C. S. MATHELA* and A. B. MELKANI

Department of Chemistry, Kumaun University,
Nainital-263 002

VASU DEV

California State Polytechnic University,
Pomona 91768, U.S.A.

and

ALBERT T. BOTTINI

University of California, Davis, CA 95616, U.S.A.

Manuscript received 11 June 1986, revised 5 January 1987,
accepted 5 June 1987

MANY plants, including members of the genus *Nepeta*, have been reported to yield ursolic acid **1a** often in combination with its isomer oleanolic acid **1b**^{1–3}. We describe here the isolation

and identification of 98% pure **1a** as its monohydrate from *N. leucophylla* Benth.

1a; R₁=H; R₂=CH₃
1b; R₁=CH₃; R₂=H

The leaves of *N. leucophylla* were collected from Nainital in the month of May. Identification was confirmed by Y. P. S. Pangtey, Kumaun University (Herbarium no. 708) and P. P. Mnyal, F.R.I., Dehradun (Accession no. 153826). The dried and powdered leaves (785 g) were extracted with diethyl ether to yield a white microcrystalline product (1.7 g, 0.2%), m.p. 262–63° with gas evolution, m.p. 237–89° after drying at 110° in vacuum, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ 64.2° (c 0.8, 1 N alc. KOH). Tlc (silica gel G; 5% CH₃OH in CHCl₃) indicated the presence of no more than one compound. The EIHR mass spectrum of the product indicated that it is **1a**, **1b** or a combination of the two⁴, and its elemental analysis and melting behavior suggested that it is **1a**.H₂O⁵. Its ir spectrum was in good agreement with that reported⁶ for **1a** and its 360 MHz ¹H nmr spectrum was consistent with the reported 60MHz spectra of related urs-12-enes^{6,7}. The 360MHz spectrum allows us to give more accurate values of δ 0.946 and 0.860, *J* 6.4Hz, for the doublets due to methyls at C₂₉ and C₃₀. Further, lack of absorption of δ 1.15 due to the C₂₇ methyl of olean-12-enes related to **1b**⁶, allows us to place an upper limit of 2% on the amount of **1b** in the *N. leucophylla* product. Resonance frequencies in the ¹³C nmr spectrum, with the exception of that due to the nondiagnostic carboxyl carbon, differed by no more than 0.3 ppm from resonances reported for methyl ursolate⁸.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported in part by grants from U.G.C., New Delhi to one of the authors (C.S.M.). HRMS were obtained at the Mass Spectrometry Laboratory, Facility for Advanced Instrumentation, A. D. Jones, Director, U. C., Davis; the ZAB-HS mass spectrometer, VG Analytical, used for determination of the spectra was purchased in part by NIH Division of Research Resources Grant RR 01460. ¹H nmr spectra were obtained at the U.C., Davis NMR Facility. The authors are grateful to Professor M. J. Minch, University of the Pacific, for obtaining the ¹³C nmr spectra.

References

1. C. VON CARSTENN-LICHTERFELDE, B. RODRIGUEZ and S. VALERDE, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, 12, 3002.

2. R. TSCHESCHE and G. WULFF, *Prog. Chem. Org. Natural Prod.*, 1973, 30, 461.
3. K. G. LEWIS and D. J. TUCKER, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1983, 36, 2297.
4. H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, J. M. WILSON and C. DJERASSI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3688.
5. F. D. DODGE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 1917.
6. R. SAVOIR, R. OTTINGER, B. TURSCH and G. CHURDOGLU, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1967, 76, 371.
7. G. ROMEO, P. GIANNETTO and M. C. AVERSA, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1977, 9, 29.
8. S. SEO, Y. TOMITA and K. TORI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 7.

Amino Acids from *Leucas lanata*

B. DINDA*, U. K. JANA and J. CHATTERJEE

Department of Chemistry,
Calcutta University Post Graduate Centre,
Agartala-799 004

Manuscript received 18 August 1986, revised 4 May 1987,
accepted 19 May 1987

THE genus *Leucas*¹ belonging to *Labiatae* family comprises 100 species found throughout the world. The species, *Leucas lanata* Benth.^{1,2} is found in Tripura along with *L. aspera* Spreng. It is a perennial herb with much branches from a stout rootstock having white flowers in axillary dense whorls, which have calyx straight mouths and setaceous bracts. Tender shoots are used as vegetables and leaves, and used medicinally¹. To find out the diet value of the plant with respect to amino acid content, we investigated chemically for the first time the aerial parts of the plant and isolated fourteen amino acids among which six are essential. In this communication, we report the isolation, characterisation and relative occurrence of these amino acids.

The aerial parts of the plant, *L. lanata* were collected from Khayerpur area of Agartala in September, 1985. The air-dried milled aerial parts (1 kg) were extracted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) and 90% ethanol successively in a Soxhlet for 48 h each. The alcoholic extract was concentrated and decolourised by refluxing with a little charcoal. The greenish filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure to a gummy residue (30.2 g). A part of the residue (1.5 g) was chromatographed^{3,4} through Amberlite IR 120(H). Working up the column for neutral and basic amino acids as described⁵ led to the identification of lysine, threonine and histidine by co-pc with authentic samples.

Another portion of the crude residue (2.0 g) was chromatographed through Amberlite IRA 400(OH) and elution with 2 N acetic acid for basic and neutral amino acids led to the characterisation of glycine, serine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid,

hydroxy proline, proline, alanine, tyrosine, tryptophan, methionine and phenyl alanine by co-pc with authentic samples.

The relative occurrences of amino acids in μg per g of air-dried aerial parts isolated through their ninhydrin complexes and estimated colorimetrically⁶ were found to be histidine, 6.80; lysine, 4.80; threonine, 2.40; aspartic acid, 2.28; proline, 2.18; alanine, 2.01; phenylalanine, 1.98; glycine, 1.60; serine, 1.40; tyrosine, 1.05; glutamic acid, 1.01; hydroxyproline, 0.93; tryptophan, 0.75 and methionine, 0.30. The amounts of glycine and serine may be inaccurate as their bands were very close in preparative pc. Among these, histidine, lysine, threonine, phenyl alanine, tryptophan and methionine are essential amino acids for human system.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to Dr. N. K. Chakraborty, M. B. B. College, Agartala, for identification of plant species, to Prof. J. B. Ganguly, Director of this Centre and to Dr. L. M. Mukherjee, In-charge of this Department for facilities and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. B. D. DEB, "The Flora of Tripura State", Today & Tomorrow, New Delhi, 1983, Vol. 2, p. 325.
2. "The Wealth of India. A Dictionary of Indian Raw Materials and Industrial Products", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1962, Vol. 6, p. 80.
3. E. LEDERER and M. LEDERER, "Chromatography", Elsevier, New York, 1957, p. 127.
4. E. STAHL, "Thin-Layer Chromatography", 2nd. ed., Toppan, Tokyo, 1969, p. 737.
5. B. DINDA and M. K. SAHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 789.

Amino Acids from *Spilanthes paniculata*

B. DINDA* and S. GUHA

Department of Chemistry,
Calcutta University Post Graduate Centre,
Agartala-799 004

Manuscript received 7 October 1986, revised 4 May 1987,
accepted 19 May 1987

THE genus *Spilanthes*¹ belonging to *Compositae* family comprises 60 species found in tropical America and exotic in other countries. The species, *Spilanthes paniculata* Wall. ex DC.^{1,2} is found in the jhum land and waste places of Tripura. It is an annual herb of 2.5–5 cm long with many branches and yellow paleae embracing flowers. The juice of this plant is used by the tribesmen in the relief of gum pain. We investigated chemically for the first time the aerial parts of the plant and isolated twelve amino acids among which six are essen-